

Table 2. Incidence of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* in parts of rice seed.

Variety	Infection (%) in			
	Husk	Endo-sperm	Embryo	Whole seed
IR8	12	14	12	13
Intan	30	17	10	64
Palguna	13	17	14	22
Average	18	16	12	33

Effect of organic and inorganic chemicals on in vitro growth of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*

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The in vitro effect of 235 chemical compounds on the growth of 34 *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* strains was tested in agar media. The chemicals tested were al-

cohols, aldehydes, organic and inorganic salts and acids, oximes, quaternary ammonium compounds, amines, glycosides, ketones, oxides, phenolic compounds, and sulfoxides. The chemicals were tested at a concentration of 0.005% (wt/vol), and those that prevented development of all 34 strains at 0.005% were tested at lower concentrations. A multipoint inoculator was used to inoculate the media.

The most active products against *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* in vitro were ZnO,

8-hydroxyquinoline, and methylglyoxal (all inhibitory between 0.0005% and 0.001%); Cd (NO₃)₂ Cd (OOC.CH₃)₂, o-phenanthroline, 7-chloro-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-1-ethyl-3-quinoline carboxylic acid (CGA 78039), and formaldehyde (inhibitory between 0.0001% and 0.0005%). Salts of copper, nickel, and cobalt were inhibitory for all strains at concentrations between 0.001% and 0.005%. Promising compounds will be tested further in field trials at IRRI. □

embryo were separated after seeds were soaked in sterile water for 4 h and surface sterilized with 0.5% NaOCl for 10 min. *R. oryzae* was counted using the standard blotter method.

Production of inocula of *Rhizoctonia solani* on different media and media effect on disease development

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Since its inception, BRRI has screened rice varieties for resistance to sheath blight (ShB) caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*. We first used inocula prepared in potato dextrose agar (PDA) and later used inocula grown in rice:rice hull (R:RH). R: RH medium, although inexpensive and easy to prepare, often was contaminated by fungi or bacteria (probably spore forming), even after double sterilization. We tested a new media for large-scale production of *R. solani* inocula.

The media and varieties used are in Tables 1 and 2. Equal amounts of inocula were raised for inoculum production and for inoculating the rice plants. Growth characters of the fungus on different media, lesion length development/d (growth rate), and disease index (DI) at maturity were recorded for all varieties and media used.

R: RH and rice straw (RS) media gave

cohols, aldehydes, organic and inorganic salts and acids, oximes, quaternary ammonium compounds, amines, glycosides, ketones, oxides, phenolic compounds, and sulfoxides. The chemicals were tested at a concentration of 0.005% (wt/vol), and those that prevented development of all 34 strains at 0.005% were tested at lower concentrations. A multipoint inoculator was used to inoculate the media.

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Table 1. Effect of inocula prepared in different media on *Rhizoctonia solani* growth and sheath blight development.

Media	Growth character				Sheath blight development	
	Mycelial	Sclerotial initiation ^a	Sclerotia production	Contamination %	Rate (mm/d) ^b	DI ^c
R:RH (1:2)	Slow	11	Low	Moderate	13.7 a	5.1 a
RS	Slow	11	Low	Low	12.3 a	4.8 a
RC (green)	Medium	6	High	Nil	14.1 a	4.6 ab
WH	Fast	5	Moderate	Nil	13.8 a	5.0 a
RC:WH (1:1)	Fast	5	High	Nil	12.1 a	4.7 ab
RC:WH (2:1)	Fast	5	High	Nil	14.9 a	5.0 a
RC:WH (1:2)	Fast	5	Moderate	Nil	13.0 a	4.8 a
PDA	Very fast	2	High	Low	13.4 a	4.4 b

^a Indicates days after inoculation. ^b Measured as mean lesion length development in mm/day. ^c DI = disease index (severity), measured on a scale of 0-9.

Table 2. Effect of inocula of *Rhizoctonia solani* prepared in three media on sheath blight development on 8 rice varieties.

Variety inoculated	Disease development as lesion length in mm/day ^a				Disease ^b reaction
	PDA	WH	RC	Mean	
BR1	16.0	21.7	25.5	21.1 a	S
IR8	20.4	18.7	18.6	19.2 ab	MS
Chianung Sen Yu-6	19.2	19.1	19.2	19.2 ab	MS
BR3	19.6	17.0	20.1	18.9 ab	MS
Dular	18.5	17.6	17.7	17.9 b	MR
Dharial	19.0	18.7	16.1	17.9 b	MR
BR8	13.8	12.6	13.4	13.3 b	MR
BR9	11.6	12.0	12.6	12.1 b	MR

^a Mean of 32 isolates. ^b S = susceptible, MS = moderately susceptible, MR = moderately resistant.

slow mycelial growth, late sclerotial initiation, low sclerotia production, and higher contamination (Table 1). Fungus growth on PDA was significantly better. However, the media appeared to have no significant effect on rate of disease development, although DI was less for PDA

inocula than for other inocula. When 8 rice varieties were inoculated at boot stage with inocula from 32 isolates grown in PDA, water hyacinth (WH), and rice culm (RC), type of media had less effect on rate of disease development. However, varieties significantly differed in mean

rate of disease development. This varietal difference was correlated with varietal disease reaction (Table 2). The findings suggest that RC, WH, or a mixture of RC and WH in any proportion are appropriate for large-scale production of *R. solani* inocula. □

Effect of rice plant age on rice tungro virus symptoms

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We conducted a pot culture experiment with susceptible TN1 to determine the influence of rice plant age at the time of tungro (RTV) infection on incubation period and nitrogen metabolism. Plants were inoculated with viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* when they were 15, 30, 45, 60, and 75 d old. Incubation period, and leaf and grain nitrogen content are in the table.

Symptoms appeared 18.3 d after inoculation of 75-d-old plants vs 8 d for 15-d-

Effect of age of tungro virus infection on rice plants.

Age at inoculation (d)	Incubation period (d)	Leaves/tiller	Leaf length (cm)	Leaf nitrogen (%)	Grain nitrogen (%)	
15	8.0	4.9	22.9	1.3	1.0	
30	9.0	5.4	30.0	1.3	1.2	
45	9.5	5.5	34.3	1.2	1.2	
60	15.0	5.7	40.2	1.1	1.3	
75	18.3	5.6	47.5	0.9	1.4	
Control	—	5.7	49.4	0.7	1.4	
Critical difference (P = 0.05)		1.6	0.3	3.3	0.08	0.07

old plants. There were significantly fewer leaves/tiller on plants inoculated at 15 d and leaf length was 53.6% less. As plant age at infection increased, there was a gradual increase in leaf length, but the leaves of all infected plants were significantly shorter than those of healthy

plants. Infection of 75-d-old plants did not significantly reduce leaf length. Leaf nitrogen content was significantly higher for infected plants than for healthy ones. Nitrogen content of grains was significantly lower in plants infected at age 60 d than in healthy plants. □

Effect of growth regulators on tungro infection

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When growth regulators indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) and gibberellic acid (GA) were applied to detached rice leaves or sprayed on rice plants, they prevented rice tungro virus (RTV) infection. We evaluated the effect of IAA and GA root or seedling dip on RTV infection.

Roots of 15-day-old TN1 seedlings raised inside an insect-proof cage were washed with water, then immersed in GA and IAA solutions at different concentrations for 1 h. The roots of control plants were dipped in water. Seedlings were transplanted in earthen pots and after 3 d were inoculated with RTV by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens*. After 24 h inoculation feeding, insects were removed from the seedlings.

In another experiment, the entire

seedling was immersed for 1 h in the growth regulator solutions and then inoculated. The control seedlings were dipped in water. The number of infected plants in each treatment was counted (see table). Percent of infected plants after root dipping gradually decreased as IAA concentration increased. At 400 ppm IAA, only 40% of the plants developed RTV symptoms. Against tungro, IAA was more effective than GA. □

Effect of plant growth regulators on RTV infection, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	RTV infection (%)	
	Root dip	Plant dip
IAA 200 ppm	55	45
IAA 300 ppm	50	30
IAA 400 ppm	40	25
GA 400 ppm	65	40
Control	90	80
CD (P = 0.05)	10.2	5.9

Axonopus compressus, a grass host for *Rhizoctonia solani*

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Axonopus compressus is a common perennial grass weed that grows on boundary ridges of rice fields and in farmyards in Jalpaiguri and Cooch Behar districts of West Bengal. Both districts have more than 3,000 mm annual rainfall. Soil is generally acidic. In Aug-Sep 1982, *Rhi-*

zoctonia solani, a rice sheath blight pathogen, was found infecting *A. compressus* and border rows of rice plants. On artificial inoculation, isolates of *R. solani* from *A. compressus* and rice plants infected both plant species. *R. solani* apparently survives and multiplies on *A. compressus*, from which infection spreads to rice. □

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